

Investigating the mechanisms of air-water gas transfer by quantitative imaging techniques: history, current progress and remaining challenges

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“On the open sea, the microlayer is almost inaccessible to direct physical measurements” [Hasse, 1997]. Indeed, classical mass balance techniques, which estimate mean transfer velocities over large spatial and temporal scales, are only suitable for a parametrization of the transfer process with the parameters controlling it [Jähne, 2009]. Direct insight into the mechanisms of air-water gas transfer, however, is given by techniques that provide a spatio-temporal quantitative imaging of all the parameters that determine the mass exchange process within the microlayer at the water surface [Sideman and Hijikata, 1993]. This includes the turbulent shear flow, concentration fields of dissolved gases, and the shape of the ocean surfaces undulated by wind-driven waves. At higher wind speeds, when waves are breaking, it is also required to visualise bubbles and droplets.

While numerical approaches and also all kinds of flow visualization techniques in general have made significant progress in the last years, progress in quantitative imaging to investigate air-sea mass transfer is still slow, because imaging techniques are experimentally very demanding even in laboratory facilities. This is because the interface is moving, being deformed by waves and sometimes breaks. Thus the lack of adequate quantitative imaging techniques is one of the major obstacles in gaining a better understanding of the mechanisms of air-sea gas transfer. Most previous investigations were limited to the simpler case of flat free water surfaces and used only various kinds of bottom-generated turbulence. This paper reviews quantitative imaging techniques for the experimental study of the mechanisms of air-water gas exchange at surfaces, which experience wind-induced surface stress and are undulated by short wind waves. Recent progress is reported and remaining challenges are pointed out. The techniques reviewed include imaging of short wind waves, flow fields, concentration fields, and - only briefly - also optical imaging of bubbles and droplets.

1. Shape of the water surface (imaging of short wind waves)

Imaging techniques for wind waves are one of the oldest visualization techniques. Since more than a century, stereo wave imaging has been used. However, stereo imaging is not suitable for short wind waves including capillary waves. Techniques based on light reflection from the water surface (Stilwell photography) were more successful. In the laboratory, imaging techniques based on refraction of light at the water surface were successfully used and were applied in many wind/wave facilities. Recently, high-speed cameras with more than 300 frames/s were used to record image sequences, from which wavenumber/frequency spectra could be computed. Imaging of short wind waves in the field still remains a major challenge. Recent approaches include a polarimetric extension of Stilwell photography and techniques similar to the classical sun glitter technique of Cox & Munk, replacing the sun by artificial light sources.

2. Imaging of flow fields [Grue et al., 2004, Tropea et al., 2007]

Quantitative flow visualization is a rapidly evolving field of research (see, e.g., the biannual international symposium on flow visualization, ISFV). There are well-established techniques, such as particle imaging velocimetry (PIV) and particle tracking velocimetry (PTV) and the current research effort is going towards techniques that extend these planar light sheet techniques to three-dimensional, three velocity component (3D3C) measuring techniques. The major challenge for flow field visualization close to the interface is the amplitude of the surface motion, which is much larger than the resolution required to resolve the velocity gradient within the viscous boundary layer. Thus either high-resolution techniques, wave following systems, or special imaging techniques are used that estimate the distance of a particle from the water surface. Another challenge is the separation of the orbital wave motion from the turbulent motions. Of much interest for the theory of air-water gas transfer are also techniques, which measure the surface flow convergence, and direct imaging of the wind stress at the surface.

3. Imaging of concentration fields

Quantitative imaging of concentration fields includes thermal imaging and laser induced fluorescence. Although thermal imaging allows only measurements at the interface because of the short penetration depth of infrared radiation into water, so-called active thermographic techniques, where the water surface is heated by infrared radiation are capable of estimating the time constant for heat exchange across the aqueous thermal boundary layer, the net heat flux, and the wind stress at the water surface. Direct measurements of the temperature gradient by at least two wavelengths have been proposed already long ago, but were – so far – not really successful. Direct imaging of concentration fields of dissolved gases are either based on fluorescence quenching of dissolved oxygen or fluorescent pH indicators with the use of acid or alkaline gases. With both techniques, significant progress has been made in the last years, and new techniques are on the horizon.

Remaining challenges

Quantitative imaging techniques are the key technique for a better understanding of the mechanisms of air-water gas transfer. However, a lot of research work is still ahead

- a) to extend these techniques to true three-dimensional visualization techniques,
- b) to combine them together at the same footprint,
- c) to develop methods for quantitative comparisons with numerical studies,
- d) and to apply them in the field at least to the extent that it can be verified that the laboratory studies capture all mechanisms, which are observed at the ocean interface.

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